

First Iran Mathematician: Maryam Mirzakhani

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Abstract

The loss of Maryam Mirzakhani creates an impact in many women mathematics. "My mailbox is full of the message from other women" says Ingrid Daubechies, a maths professor at Duke University. Women mathematicians from all over the world are e-mailing each other, trying to comfort each other. It is heartbreaking news that we had to lose a gifted mathematician and wonderful role model so soon."

Introduction

Maryam Mirzakhani was an Iranian Mathematician and a Professor of Mathematics at Standford University. Her research topics included Teahmuller theory, hyperbolic geometry, ergodic theory, and symplectic geometry. In 2005, as a result of her research, she was honored as "Brilliant 10" in popular science's fourth annual where she was acknowledged as one of the top 10 young minds who have pushed their fields in innovative directions.

Life History

Mirzakhani was born on 12th May 1977 in Tehran, Iran. she attended Tehran Farzanegan School, a part of the National Organization for the Development of Exceptional Talents (NODET). In her school days, she won gold medal for Mathematics in the Iranian National Olympiad. That helped to pass the National College entrance exams. In 1994, Mirzakhani got a gold medal in the International Mathematics Olympiad in Hong Kong. She was the first female Iranian student to Score 41 out of 42 points. In 1995, she became the first Iranian student to win two gold medals in International Mathematics Olympiad held in Canada.

Mirzakhani and Zaverah were the first women to compete in the Iranian National Mathematical Olympiad and won gold and silver medals respectively in 1995.

Education

In 1999, she obtained a Bachelor degree in Mathematics from the Sharif University of Technology. She received recognition from the American Mathematical Society for her work 'Shor's Algorithm'. She went to the United States for higher studies and earned Ph.D in 2004 from Harvard University. Where she worked under the supervision of Medalist Curtis T.Memullen At Harvard, she used to take her class notes in Farsi.

Career

Mirzakhani was a 2004 research fellow of the Clay Mathematics Institute and Professor at Princeton University. In 2009 She became a Professor at Stanford University.

Mirzakhani made several contributions to the theory of moduli spaces of Riemann Surfaces. Mirzakhani solved the problem of counting simple closed geodesics on hyperbolic Riemann Surfaces by finding a relationship to volume calculations on moduli space. Geodesics are the natural generalization of the idea of “Straight line” to “Curved Spaces”. Formally, a curve is a geodesic if no slight deformation can make it shorter, closed geodesics are geodesics which are also close up into loops. A closed geodesic is simple if it does not cross itself.

Her subsequent work focused on Teichmüller dynamics of moduli space. In particular, she was able to prove the long-standing conjecture. One can construct a simple earthquake map by cutting a surface along a finite number of disjoint simple closed geodesics, sliding the edges of each of these cut each other by some amount, and closing the surface back up. One can imagine the surface being cut by strike – slip faults. Where one has an infinite number of geodesics and instead of attaching a positive real number to each geodesic one puts a measure on them.

In 2014, with Alex Eskin and Amir Mohammed, Mirzakhani proved that complex geodesics and their closures in moduli space are surprisingly regular, rather than irregular or fractal. The closures of complex geodesics are algebraic objects defined in terms of polynomials and therefore they have certain rigidity properties, which is analogous to a celebrated result that Marina Ratner arrived at in 1990. The International Mathematical Union said in its press release that “It is astounding to find that the rigidity in homogeneous spaces has an echo in the inhomogeneous world of moduli space.

Mirzakhani was awarded ‘Fields Medal’ in 2014 for ‘her outstanding contributions to the dynamics and geometry of Riemann surfaces and their moduli spaces. The award was made in Seoul at the International Congress of Mathematicians on 13 August. At the time of the award, Jordan Ellenberg explained her research to a popular audience.

Mirzakhani was diagnosed with breast cancer during 2013 to 2016, the cancer spread to her bones and liver and she died on 14 July 2017 at the age of 40 at Stanford Hospital in Stanford California.

Conclusion

Numerous obituaries and tributes were published about Maryam Mirzakhani. As a result of advocacy carried out by the women’s committee within the Iranian Mathematical Society, the International Council for Science has agreed to declare Maryam Mirzakhani’s birthday May 12 as ‘International Women in Mathematics Day’ in respect of her memory.

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